

AN ANALYSIS OF FINANCING SMEs IN THE ROMANIAN ECONOMY DURING AND POST COVID-19 CRISIS

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Abstract

Purpose – The aim of this paper is to show how financing SMEs has changed during and post COVID-19 pandemic in Romania. The paper analyzes how the financing of SMEs changed in the period of Covid and what are the perspective after Covid.

Methodology/approach -The article uses quantitative research using reports published by Research Institutes or professional associations.

Findings – Romanian SMEs tend to use self-financing as the main source of financing their activity and the alternatives sources tend to become more interesting. As a result, the factoring, leasing and crowd-funding market are increasing.

Research limitations/implications – The research offers a non complete image regarding the financing of the Romanian SMEs after the COVID crisis due to the limited access to data regarding the sources used by companies.

Practical implications – The paper offers to the interested parties (researchers, entrepreneurs etc.) ideas about alternatives sources of financing besides the traditional ones and the way that they can be used to optimes the capital structure of the companies.

Originality/value – The research offers an analysis of the alternative sources of financing for Romanian SMEs and propose solutions to consider in case of future crisis.

Key words: financing, SMEs, crowdfunding

Introduction

The paper analyzes the data regarding the main sources for small and medium enterprises comparing the situation before the COVID-19 crisis and after.

For start-ups, typically money is raised from the 3 F (family, friends and business angels). They are not eligible for other sources of financing like leasing, factoring, bank financing due to the fact that they don't meet the criteria requested by the banks or financial institution, especially in terms of financial indicators, collaterals etc.

Finding financing it is crucial for start-ups (Cassar, 2004), not only in time of crisis but also in, as we say now, "normal life". There is a limited number of studies regarding the response of entrepreneurs to the changes brought by a crisis, but as previous research shows (Festel, 2011) most of the startups doesn't understands or preview all the consequences that come with a crisis, interruption in production, lack of capital, lack in human resources etc.

Financing stages for SMEs

Different types of financing are adequate for different stages of companies: seed financing, start-up, venture capital, mezzanine financing and loan bridges and initial public offering (IPO).

Pre-Seed funding is the first step in financing a company and sometimes is not taken into discussion because it is a phase of financing when the company doesn't exist yet, when capital is usually raised from entrepreneur's own resources, family and friends and investors known as funding angels (Gourinchas, Kalemlı-Özcan, Penciakova, Sander, 2020). Funding angels are a viable option for founders, because besides their capital, they bring their knowledge, business network and they invest time in the operational activities of the new future company.

For the next stage of financing, seed financing, when company seek to raise capital, they usually tend to reach to business angels, because at this point, they are not eligible for loans, as they don't have any financial results or collaterals to present. At this point, the capital raised by a start-up can vary from 10.000 USD up to 2.000.000 USD according to Halo Report in 2020.

Another option for this stage, could be nonrefundable founds, governmental programs etc.

Venture capital is suitable for companies which already reached a certain maturity and they want to expand, develop new products, enter new markets etc. Those companies can turn to several source of financing, depending their field of activity, their type of investment. Literature split the venture capital in rounds, series A, B and C.

Series A for a company means an important step in its development, because it shows that the company has a minimum viable product (MVP). The capital invested in this stage is up to 10.000.000 USD (EUR).

Series B and C are taking the companies to the next level, preparing the business if this is what is intended to IPO. The amount of capital raised in series B and C is up to 50-60 million series B and up to 100 million series C.

Traditional and alternative sources of financing for Romanian SMEs

A survey conducted by the European Investment Fund in 2019 shows that Business Angels are oriented to pre-seed and start-up companies who activate in Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning and E-commerce, FinTech and there is also interest in sustainability and cleantech.

In 2019, before the beginning of the Covid pandemic, the business angels questioned in the survey appreciated that the current business environment is good/very good and 57% considered that it will remain the same, and 33% even anticipated that it will improve (Kuckertz, 2020), so nobody expected the Black Swan event – the Covid.

SME have been, as the whole world, surprised by the Covid crise and they reacted differently in terms of liquidity. There were companies who anticipate great long term negative impact (Thorgren and Williams, 2020) and those who considered there will be little impact.

The companies who anticipate that the crises will affect their liquidities for a long period of time took measures like: deferring investment, try to access governmental founds, reduce their costs, renegotiate terms of contracts, loans etc.

Romanian companies, like all other companies were strongly affected by the Covid pandemic, and even if all types of business were affected, SMEs suffered mostly because they don't have capital reserves, low level of assets, not very innovative and they usually have a low rate of productivity. All conducted researches estimate a high rate of bankruptcy because of Covid [6].

The paper presents the financing of the SMEs and the methodology consist in an analyze of the main source of financing for this companies: self-financing, loans, nonrefundable founds, business angels, leasing and factoring and crowdfunding.

Self-financing

Self-financing is the most used and known source of financing and all data shows that all companies are using their own resources to finance their activities. And this tendency is more pregnant in the tech sector. The pandemic hit harder in this domain, and a study made in 2021 on 117 Romanian tech start-up shows that 70% of the tech companies were affected by the Covid crisis. The main problem for this companies is seeking new financing sources due to the fact that self-financing has a big disadvantage, meaning is limited and in time of crisis this aspect is more challenging.

The cash-flow difficulties were a reality for all SMEs and all governments tried to find solutions in the pandemic to help business overcome this period. The Romanian government adopted a series of measures like non refundable funds, tax reduction or no penalties for delays in tax payments etc.

Loan

As mentioned before, loan is not a source of financing for all companies, because start-up has practically no access to this type of financing due to the lack of collaterals, no previous financial statements, so they are high risks for banks. Nonfinancial companies use loans for financing their current activities or their investments, but the Covid crisis made the SMEs more cautious regarding new loans due to the fact that not all activities recuperated, there is a lot of uncertainty on the capital market. A study conducted on 11000 companies, made by BNR shows that a high percentage of companies used reinvestment of profit, self-financing, selling their own assets or loans from the company owners and a reduction in accessing bank loans, even lines of credits. Compared to 2020 the percentage of the business who didn't use any financing from bank or financial institutions (IFN) is increasing from 75% up to 77%.

Also, the study shows that bank loan was used as a source of financing only by 7% of the companies and a big problem that this study shows is that less than 1% of the SMEs access European funds. This situation indicated the fact that companies don't benefit from the financial leverage because they rely on their own capital and also the low rate of European funds absorption. This situation can be observed in Fig 1.

Fig 1

The lack of interest for bank loan for SMEs has been explained by the collateral requested by the bank (value or type), high level of interest rate and bank commission and bureaucracy. Another observation that can be made based on this research is that nor leasing or factoring are used for financing the company's activities and this is a topic that can be investigated in another paper.

The Romanian government came with a response to the economical crise under the form of a financing program known as IMM Invest Romania, which provides access to bank loan for companies and the aid consist in providing collateral up to 90% of the loan amount, no interest or other initial cost for 8 months, no risk commission and the amount of the loan is up to 10 million lei for investments and 5 million for working capital. Besides IMM INVEST, small companies can obtain financing through IMM Leasing, IMM Factor or Agro IMM Invest, depending on their activity or type of investment.

Business angels

They are known as successful entrepreneurs that are interested in finding new possibility for investment and they are a solution for incipient business that are searching for financing, because their own

resources are insufficient and banks or other types of financing are out of reach due to the lack of collateral or financial statements.

Before COVID-19, data shows that, more than 60% of the early-stage investments in European companies are made by angel investors (EBAN 2019) but some signals have been mentioned by Luigi Amati, president of Business Angels Europe saying that if angel investing breaks down, you break down the whole pipeline of development”.

There is limited information regarding the activity of business angels during the pandemic period due to the fact that not all business angels are part of registered network, nor all their activity is public.

An analysis of the Romanian companies during the Covid period showed that the newcomers (start-up and unicorns) fund this period as beneficial for financing through BA because they perceived this crisis only as a short market disruption. It was a little more difficult for companies in a later stage to find financing but the report on venture capital on 2021 shows that average amount invested in seed rounds in 2021 has almost doubled in size, going from €591k in 2020 to €1.07M (taking into account the FlowX round).

Fig. 2

Before Covid, In Romania business angels oriented their investment in companies related to E-Commerce, 3 from 5 rounds were dedicated to this type of business. The medical crisis didn't interrupted the growth of E-commerce, FinTech but two other types of business attracted the attention of BA: Digital Health and EdTech. In the medical area, digitalization wasn't a new topic but the Covid crises accelerated this process, SanoPass and Peditel are some of the names with big plans for 2021.

Leasing and factoring

These two types of financing are suitable for working capital financing or equipment financing. As seen in fig. 1, companies use leasing and factoring in a very small percentage (less than 10%), even though these solutions can help overcome liquidity problems in crisis's periods.

As financial and operating leasing are well-known and used by Romanian companies for financing equipment investment, the paper emphasizes on a special type of leasing, the sell and lease back. This type of leasing is suitable for companies who want to develop or continue their production, they own large amount of tangible assets but they need capital to buy raw materials, pay salaries and they can't use bank loans. This was, actually, the situation for a lot of Romanian SMEs during Covid crises.

The solution to continue production, satisfying their clients and keep their employees could have been the sale and lease back financing. This is a contract that combines two transactions simultaneously: a sell and a lease. The company seeks a leasing company (investor) and sells her tangible assets to the

investor and at the same times leases (rents) back the assets for a determined period of time (up to 48 months usually). The operation can be analyzed in fig 3 The lease contract is a contract with a firm option to buy all the items at the end of the contract. This solution provides the company with the necessary cash-flow, maintaining in the same time the use of the equipment, in order to continue its activity.

Fig. 3

As for factoring, even though this type of financing is known for several years now, there are many SMEs that are not even aware of this financing alternative. A study made by the Factoring Romanian Association (ARF) shows that the factoring market grown in 2021 with 20% compared to 2020, reaching a volume of 6 billion euros. The same study shows that only 21% of this market is represented by companies with a turnover less than 5 million euros, most of the factoring transactions (42%) were made by companies with a turnover > 50 million euros.

Another fact that can be observed and mentioned regarding the factoring market was the reverse factoring that increase in 2021 with 28% with an amount of 2,3 billion euros (more that 1/3 of the factoring market). This is a great news because reverse factoring is a solution for very small companies depending on a single or limited number of clients, which can only use factoring through this type of factoring, because they are not eligible for traditional factoring.

Also, the European market shows the same trends after the decrease in the pandemic period, the overall volume reached €2.0 trillion, up from €1.8 trillion in 2020, with international factoring comprising 23% of the total value according to the data collated by the EUF Economic and Statistic Committee for 2021.

This growth is explained by multiple factors: the rebound of European economy, rising prices for raw materials, energy, shipping cost, inflation, but the growth of factoring market is much higher than the inflation and the increase of GDP and that means that in time of crises factoring starts to appear as a reliable source of short-term financing.

Crowdfunding

Financing a company through crowdfunding is one of the newest solutions for raising capital. This type of financing is suitable for pre-seed or start-up companies, which are seeking for funds, but can't access non-refundable funds or bank loans, because they are in a phase that they aren't complying with the requests for obtaining this kind of financing. Crowdfunding means that a company is raising capital through its potential clients, who are "paying" in advance for a product which is launched using an internet platform. Besides raising capital, the companies can benefit from the accumulated know-how and they validate their ideas.

Globally, the most known and used platform for crowdfunding are Kickstarter and Indiegogo. In Europe, there is a major interest to normalize this type of financing, especially to protect the persons who invest in those start-ups and beginning with November 2021, a new Regulation has been introduced in EU, including Romania. But for now, in Romania there is a legislation regarding crowdfunding (Law 244/2022), applicable beginning with 6th August 2022 who regulate aspects like: an authority who survey the crowdfunding platforms, sanctions and penalties for bad behavior on the crowdfunding platforms,

the condition for the transfer of equity (social parts) in companies financed through crowdfunding and in case of indivisible or nonliquid social parts the creation of a special purpose vehicle (SPV).

According to statistics, in Romania in 2022 the transaction value for crowdfunding financing is projected to reach 0,71 m in 2022, with a decrease of 16,3% compare to 2021. This decrease can be also the result of the impact of the Ukraine war on the market. The most known Romanian platforms for crowdfunding are: Startarium and Seedblink (the first equity crowdfunding platform develop in Romania). Also, the company High Crowd Estate Technologies has announced the launch of a new crowdfunding platform in the real estate sector.

This shows that crowdfunding is a solution who is getting more and more interest for start-ups and also for businesses who intend to scale up and are in need of capital.

Conclusions

Financing business's activities is one of the main managerial decisions for a company and for small and medium enterprises raising capital and finding resources to finance investments and operating activities is a challenge especially in time of crisis like Covid-19 pandemic. Romanian SMEs like all companies were severely affected by the changes in the economic market brought by the medical crises. They were forced to adapt to the new way of doing business, implement digitalization, remote labor and also search for new financing solutions, besides the traditional ones like self-financing and bank loans. Leasing and factoring market are increasing, which is a sign that companies implement more and more alternatives solutions like reverse factoring, or as proposed in this paper, in time of crises lease-back could be a viable solution for short term financing for companies with high amount of tangible assets. Crowdfunding is also a tool to be considered, for start-ups especially.

It is important for SMEs to adapt their way of doing business and in terms of financing, to reach for alternatives sources because crisis like Covid-19 pandemic or Ukraine war will happen in the future and they have to be prepared for them.

References

Cassar G

2004

"The financing of business start-ups ", J. Bus. Venturing, 19 (2), pp. 261-283

Festel, G

2011

"Founding angels as early-stage investment model to foster biotechnology start-ups", Journal of Commercial Biotechnology 17, 165–171 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1057/jcb.2011.2>

Gourinchas P-O, Kalemli-Özcan Şebnem, Penciakova V, Sander N.

2020

"COVID-19 and SME Failures. Cambridge", MA; 2020 Sep. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w27877>

Kuckertz, et al

2020

"A rapid response to the COVID-19 pandemic", <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbvi.2020.e00169> Journal of Business Venturing Insights 13: e00169

Thorgren S, Williams TA.

2020

"Staying alive during an unfolding crisis: How SMEs ward off impending disaster", Journal of Business Venturing Insights. 2020 Nov;14:e00187. doi: 10.1016/j.jbvi.2020.e00187. Epub 2020 Jul 26. PMID: PMC7382927.